

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE INTERFACE MODIFICATION OF REINFORCING PARTICLES IN AgSnO₂ COMPOSITE ELECTRICAL CONTACT MATERIAL

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Abstract: A novel AgSnO₂ electrical contact material with reinforcing tin oxide particles directionally aligned in matrix silver in a fiber-like manner was obtained through mechanical alloying and precursor technique in the previous paper. By studying their scanning electron microscope (SEM) photos, this paper discusses the formation mechanism for the surface morphology of the precursor particles. And then characterization and analysis were made by transmission electron microscope (TEM) and chemical analysis method. By using transmission electron microscope (TEM) and high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM), it is discovered that a thin film formed on the surface of SnO₂ particles. Further study by chemical analysis and Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometer (ICP) analysis demonstrates that there was a significant change of Sn content after mechanical alloying process, which indicates that by adding PEG 6000 additive during mechanical alloying process, the tin oxide on particle surface was reduced and wettability between matrix silver and tin oxide was improved.

Keywords: *surface modification, microstructure control, AgSnO₂, PEG 6000 additive*

1 General Introduction

Being non-toxic and environment-friendly and having high resistance to welding and arc erosion, AgSnO₂ contact material has unparalleled comprehensive properties and has experienced rapid development in recent years [1-5]. However, SnO₂ has exceedingly high hardness so that AgSnO₂ composite material has very poor

workability. In addition, with very good thermostability, SnO₂ hardly decomposes under arc attack and tends to rise up to and aggregate on contact surface under electromagnetic stirring as it has poor wettability with molten silver [6-7]. The nonconductive SnO₂ aggregate leads to higher contact resistance and as a result higher temperature rise under continuous current seriously worsening electrical properties.

Preparation method for AgSnO₂ electrical contact material with fibrous composite structure mentioned in prior study [8] goes as follows: prepare

AgSnO₂(60wt%) composite precursor particles by mechanically alloying SnO₂ and silver powder, mix precursor particles with silver in a proportion of 1 to 4, press, and sinter the obtained powder mixture; then process the sintered body by hot-extrusion and drawing, which make precursor particles in the matrix silver flow with the softened silver and drawn apart with certain amount of deformation and consequently SnO₂ is directionally aligned along the extrusion and drawing direction in fiber-like manner; finally produce the novel AgSnO₂(60wt%) composite electrical contact material and components. The as-prepared AgSnO₂ composite electrical contact material has a low resistivity of 2.08 μΩ•cm and a high elongation of 24%. Other properties such as welding resistance, arc erosion resistance, electrical properties etc are greatly improved. Problems such as poor workability, high cost and electrical degradation were settled for AgSnO₂ material. In the following part, TEM and ICP were utilized to analyze the effect of surface modification of the reinforcing particles prepared by the above-mentioned method from a microscopic view.

2 Analysis of the characteristics of precursor particle morphology

Micro-morphology of AgSnO₂(60wt%) composite precursor particles prepared by mechanical alloying is presented in Fig 1a, in which each big spherical particle is a nano-agglomerate composed of numerous smaller nano-particles. This nano-agglomerate has notably different micro-morphology from pure silver particles and SnO₂ particles (as shown in Fig 1b, 1c). It is speculated that under influence of mechanical alloying and the addition of organic medium PEG, oxidation-

reduction reaction takes place at the interface between SnO₂ and silver, and a thin layer of Ag-Sn alloy forms on the surface of SnO₂ nano-particles (as shown in Fig 2). Therefore, silver-coated with a silver (shell)-SnO₂ (core) structure is obtained. And silver-coated SnO₂ tends to aggregate to form precursor particles as shown in Fig 1a, resulting in enhanced wettability between SnO₂ and silver.

Fig.1 (a) SEM photo of AgSnO₂(60wt%) composite precursor particles (50000 ×); (b) SEM photo of silver powder (2000 ×); (c) SEM photo of SnO₂ nano-particles (2000×)

Fig.2 Schematic diagram of formation mechanism for AgSnO₂(60wt%) composite precursor particles

3 Analysis and characterization

3.1 TEM

Transmission electron microscope (TEM) and high resolution transmission electron microscope

(HRTEM) were adopted to examine microstructure of composite precursor particles. Micro-morphology and microstructure images of AgSnO₂ (60wt%) composite precursor particles taken by means of TEM are presented in Fig 3a, from which we know that the monomer particle is very fine with a grain size of about 20nm. Further examination by HRTEM (Fig 3b) shows that there is a white thin film, which is assumed to be Ag-Sn alloy layer. But the composition of the white film could not be determined as the particles are too fine.

Fig.3 TEM image (a) and HRTEM image (b) of AgSnO₂ (60wt%) composite precursor particles

3.2 Chemical Analysis

Two samples of mixed powders of the same mass (silver 40wt%, SnO₂ 60wt%, and PEG 1wt%) were prepared and labeled A and B respectively; mixed powder A was not milled by high-energy ball

mill while B was milled. Then A and B powders were dissolved in tartaric acid and the insoluble substances were filtered out respectively. Then Inductively Coupled Plasma Emission Spectrometer (ICP) was utilized to measure Sn content in A and B solution.

And chemical testing was used to demonstrate that Ag-Sn alloy layer had formed. When mixed powder A and B were dissolved in tartaric acid, as SnO₂ is insoluble and only elemental Sn is soluble in tartaric acid, it is feasible to measure element Sn in the solution by ICP, which makes judgment whether SnO₂ has been reduced to elemental Sn by PEG6000. Chemical testing shows that elemental Sn in A solution (no ball milling) has a content of 0.0568% and B solution (ball milled) 0.1141%. The results prove that SnO₂ on the particle surface was reduced to elemental Sn under the reducing action of PEG6000. And under the action of high energy ball milling, alloying reaction took place between Sn and Ag so that Ag-Sn alloy was formed. Therefore, the above assumption was proved to be true.

4 Summary

(1) For the fiber-like particle reinforced AgSnO₂ electrical contact material with excellent comprehensive properties prepared in previous research, we first proposes the assumed formation mechanism for AgSnO₂ (60wt%) composite precursor particles: By the means of mechanical alloying and with the addition of reductive PEG, oxidation-reduction reaction takes place at the interface between SnO₂ and silver, and a thin layer of Ag-Sn alloy forms on the surface of SnO₂ nanoparticles. Therefore, silver-coated with a silver

(shell)-SnO₂ (core) structure is obtained. Silver-coated SnO₂ particles are extremely fine resulting in aggregates of precursor particles.

(2)Interface of the reinforcing particles was characterized by transmission electron microscope (TEM) and high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM). It is discovered that there was a thin layer on the surface of SnO₂ nanoparticles.

(3)In addition, chemical analysis and ICP measurement of Sn content before and after ball milling show that Sn element content increases significantly after ball milling. It indicates that SnO₂ has been reduced to Sn element by PEG6000. Sn and Ag metals form Ag-Sn alloy under the action of high energy ball milling. Therefore, the assumption was proved to be correct.

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